

TOPOLOGICAL OPTIMIZATION APPLIED TO COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this document is to present three examples, developed in our laboratory, where the technique of topological optimization [1] have been successfully used for problems of composite structures.

KEYWORDS: Optimum design, composites, reinforcement, orientation, lattice structures, buckling.

OPTIMAL FIBER ORIENTATION FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

The mechanical behaviour of a fibre reinforced composite structure can be modulated by varying the proportion of fibres and their orientation. Traditional design considers these properties constant within a single layer. Recent developments in manufacturing techniques such as the tow placement make it possible to fabricate composite structures that have curvilinear fibres with spatially variable volume fraction. A new optimization method of the fibre orientation and the fibre volume fraction has been developed [2].

1. The method

The method consists of minimizing a functional which includes the flexibility of the structure, the price of the material, and the weight of the structure. Depending of the case, it can also include other parameters. It works here for elastic structures but can be extend to other types of materials.

The algorithm consists of two alternating minimizations : a global one and a local one : the first one is for solving an homogenized problem of structure, where homogenized constitutive relations are known; the second one is to improve at each point the amount and the direction of fibers. The type of fibers is given, but the fiber volume is to be determined. The algorithm is convergent because, at each step, the functional is decreasing. The method leads quickly to an optimal composite structure. The resulting stress field is also obtained.

2. Some results

Up to now, several computations have been performed concerning rectangular plates (Fig1), some including holes (Fig 2). The computations have been realized using finite element method; on each element we get the optimal direction of the fibers according to the loads which have been applied, in order to minimise the displacements, that is to say the flexibility of the structure.

Following the same kind of idea, we can take into account the optimal rate of the fibers at each element of the structure. We give some of our results in the following picture.

Figure 1

Figure 2

OPTIMISATION OF AN ASSEMBLY OF COMPOSITE PLATES WITH RESPECT TO THE RELATIVE PLY THICKNESSES

Using some of classical results on local minimizations, we are working on the optimization of an industrial oriented structure: an assembly of composites plates (for example an airplane wing flap). Considering a classical industrial layout of symmetric long fibers laminates ($0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ$), we study the optimization of the compliance of such structures with respect to the relative ply thicknesses in the different plates of the assembly.

We use a model of assembly of plates compatible with the classical min-min optimization algorithm. We describe the optimization method, the 3D plate assembly model and the specific resolution of the local minimization. Then a numerical example of the optimization of an internal reinforcement of a wing flap is presented.

The plate assembly model

In this section we consider the model of the reinforcement of a 3D medium with internal and external thin elastic plates. This model, assuming that the rigidity of the reinforcement is much greater than the rigidity of the "filling" 3D medium, allows us to define a model of an assembly of plates.

We consider the reinforcement of a 3D medium with internal and external Love Kirchhoff plates. The variational formulation and energy theorems are written. It is proven that there exists a unique solution to this new 3D elasticity problem.

The numerical implementation has been performed on a simplified model for which each reinforcement is a membrane with transverse shear. We note a_{ijkl} the behavior law of the filling 3D medium, S the domain of a membrane, $b_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ and $c_{\alpha\beta}$ the respective in plane and out of plane behavior laws of the membrane.

This model leads to the introduction of a surface rigidity on 3D classical finite elements. The implementation has been performed using a 8 nodes cubic element with a linear interpolation into the open source finite element code Modulef.

Optimal design of an industrial wing flap

Composite plates in the aircraft industry are usually symmetric composite laminates with long straight fibers of equal density in each ply. The simplest case classically used is a laminate ($0^\circ, (-45^\circ, +45^\circ), 90^\circ$), with the same number of plies oriented at -45° and at $+45^\circ$. The global orientation of each laminate (i.e. the orientation of the plies at 0° with respect to the global coordinate system) is supposed to be fixed and known. We will then consider the three distributed optimization parameters :

- h_1 : thickness of all the plies at 0° ,
- h_2 : thickness of all the plies at $\pm 45^\circ$,
- h_3 : thickness of all the plies at 90° .

If we consider a total constant thickness, $h_1+h_2+h_3$ is a known value and only two distributed parameters remain.

Local minimization problem

The material parameter is assumed to be the same in each ply of the laminate. The behavior rigidity tensors of the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° oriented plies are obtained by a simple rotation. The

rigidity tensor of the laminate is obtained by integration over the thickness of the orthotropic rigidity tensor of each ply.

The local minimization is performed on the sum of the double of the local complementary energy and the local cost term. The complementary energy may be written in the form :

$$E_C^p = \frac{\alpha_1 (\beta_1 h_1 + \beta_2 h_2 + \beta_3 h_3)}{\gamma_1 (h_1^2 + h_3^2) + \gamma_2 h_2^2 + \gamma_3 h_2 (h_1 + h_3) + \gamma_4 h_1 h_3} + \frac{\alpha_2}{\delta_1 (h_1 + h_3) + \delta_2 h_2} + \frac{\alpha_3}{\zeta_1 h_1 + \zeta_2 h_2 + \zeta_3 h_3} + \frac{\alpha_4}{\xi_1 h_1 + \xi_2 h_2 + \xi_3 h_3}$$

where $\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i, \delta_i, \zeta_i, \xi_i$ are function of the material parameters and the local stress state. We can choose for example a local cost term relative to the mass of the reinforcement :

$$cost(h_1, h_2, h_3) = k \cdot (h_1 + h_2 + h_3)$$

The constraints of this local minimization problem are :

- each relative thickness must be greater than a proportion of the total thickness,
- the total thickness must be lower than a maximal value (H_{max}).

With a minimum value of 10% for the plies at $0^\circ, -45^\circ, +45^\circ$ and 90° , the constraints are written :

$$\begin{cases} h_1 \geq 0, 1(h_1 + h_2 + h_3) \\ h_2 \geq 0, 2(h_1 + h_2 + h_3) \\ h_3 \geq 0, 1(h_1 + h_2 + h_3) \\ h_1 + h_2 + h_3 \leq H_{max} \end{cases}$$

In the case of fixed and known total thickness (H_{tot}), we have : $h_1 + h_2 + h_3 = H_{tot}$. The cost term is then constant and the criterion reduces to the compliance. Only the minimal bound on the thicknesses remains. The constraints are then written :

$$\begin{cases} h_1 \geq 0, 1 H_{tot} \\ h_3 \geq 0, 1 H_{tot} \\ h_1 + h_2 \leq 0, 8 H_{tot} \end{cases}$$

This local minimizations are solved using a gradient projection method.

Numerical example

We consider the problem of the optimal design of an internal reinforcement of an airplane wingflap. A section of such an assembly of plates is presented in figure 3. The structure is made of 4 external and 1 internal plates. At the trailing edge, a rigid 3D medium models the connection between the plates. At the leading edge, the link to the wing is performed in three zones where the displacements of 6 nodes are fixed to zero. The Young's modulus of the filling 3D medium is chosen equal to 10 MPa. The material parameters of the plies are determined with kevlar fibers and an epoxy matrix using the rules of mixtures with a density of fibers of 55%.

The local minimization has been performed considering a constant total thickness. The algorithm converges within 5 iterations. We obtain a 24% decrease of the compliance and a 22% decrease of the maximal 3D displacement. The results in terms of relative thicknesses are presented in figure 4 for the internal reinforcement. In the central part of the internal reinforcement, the fibers are oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ and at 0° elsewhere. In the loaded plate, the fibers are oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ everywhere.

Schéma de l'aile

Figure 3

Figure 4

BUCKLING OPTIMIZATION OF A LATTICE CYLINDRICAL SHELL

A typical lattice structural element is presented in fig.5, showing also the basic geometric parameters of the structure. Lattice structures are usually made in the form of thin-walled cylindrical shell and consist of a system of $\pm\varphi$ (with respect to the shell axis) helical ribs and circumferential ribs. Depending on the design requirements, the structure can be made with one-side or two-side composite skins.

Fig.5: Lattice structural element

In this research, an integrated equivalent stiffness model is developed to describe a lattice structure. The proposed model allows performing analysis of the lattice structures and it is not based on the finite element method which is still of little use for overall design due to model complexity and the inability to easily changes rib geometry (angle, spacing), but rather on static, geometric and constitutive equations of shell.

As the equivalent model provide the basis of analysis, the Method of Moving Asymptotes (MMA) [3] is used to design a cylindrical lattice shell with external laminated skin. Compression axial force and the global and local buckling of the shell are considered.

1 Basic approach of the shell model

A variety of models for the analysis of the load/deformation behavior of the rib system exist that have various levels of accuracy and suitability [4]. One of the more sophisticated modelling approaches is to use a discrete system of connected beams [5]. Such a system works under tension, compression, bending and torsion loadings. The stiffness of each set of parallel ribs can be estimated individually, and then the total stiffness of a lattice is obtained by the principle of superposition. Constitutive equations, for a lattice structure with an external skin, will have the following form [5]

$$\begin{bmatrix} N \\ M \\ V \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B & C & 0 \\ C & D & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ \kappa \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix}$$

Here N and ε characterize membrane stress resultants and strains, M and κ are moments and the corresponding bending deformations, V and γ are transverse forces and shear strains.

2 Design variables and constraints

Consider a lattice cylindrical shell with given diameter D , length L and loaded with a compression axial force. Geometry of a lattice structure is shown in fig.6, where x and y are axial and circumferential coordinates, respectively. Being properly designed, this shell should have a minimum mass and satisfy buckling constraints.

Lattice structure is specified with the following independent design variables:

- Thickness of the lattice layer h_r
- Angle of helical ribs φ
- Spacing of helical ribs a_h
- Thicknesses of ribs δ_h and δ_c
- Thickness of the skin h_s
- Angle-ply of the skin φ_s

Thus, there are seven design variables that should provide the minimum value of the shell mass (ρ_h , ρ_c and ρ_s are the densities of the rib and skin materials)

$$M = \pi DL \left[h_r \left(2 \frac{\delta_h}{a_h} \rho_h + \frac{\delta_c}{a_c} \rho_c \right) + h_s \rho_s \right].$$

and satisfy the following constraint :

- Acting compression axial force should not cause the general buckling of the shell neither the local buckling of the helical ribs.

The local buckling of the ribs segments between nodes is one of the failure modes specific to lattice stiffened structures. To derive the constraint associated with this type of buckling mode, we simulate the rib segment with a plate. The connected edges are assumed to be simply supported and the edge, in contact with the skin, is assumed to be fixed (fig. 6).

Fig.6: Helical rib segment

The critical force, based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method, can be determined and the design constraint associated with the local buckling of the ribs acquires the form

$$P_{cr}^h = \frac{\pi^2 E_1^h \delta_h^3 h_r}{24 l_h^2} \left(1 + \frac{48 G_{12}^h l_h^2}{\pi^2 E_1^h h_r^2} \right)$$

where E_1^h et G_{12}^h are the elasticity and shear moduli.

Lattice structures can also experience general buckling. In non-linear analysis, analytical solutions, due to the large number of parameters affecting the limit load, are difficult to obtain. Linearized buckling equations can be obtained from equilibrium equations if we express the forces and moments that enter these equations in terms of kinematic variables. Assuming that the shell is simply supported at the ends, the design constraints associated with the shell buckling in its two modes, axisymmetric and non-symmetric, are given in [4]. Local skin buckling (the so-called pocket buckling) was never observed in lattice structures. There are two reasons for that. First, the skin panels are rather small and have specific shapes. Second, the skin is loaded, not only in compression, but also in tension by ribs inducing the effect similar to the action of internal pressure. This “pressure” stabilises the circular form, reduces the shell sensitivity to shape imperfections, and increases the critical load.

3 Optimum design

The design of a lattice shell with specified radius, length and compression axial force involves, in general, determination of rib parameters and skin parameters that satisfy the constraints discussed in the previous section. Furthermore, the design problem is typically formulated to provide a minimum mass structure. In its most general form, the problem belongs to a class of problems of non-linear mathematical programming. Hence, it is a natural development that numerical method like topological optimization is adopted for systematic design methodology of lattice structures.

To handle multiple constraints for topological optimization, large-scale mathematical-programming can be useful. Some examples of this techniques are Sequential Linear Programming SLP, Sequential Quadratic Programming SQP and the Method of Moving Asymptotes MMA. However, this work adopts MMA for the topological optimization problem.

MMA is an iterative mathematical programming that generates a sequence of improved feasible solution for a nonlinear problem. In each iteration, a dual and convex subproblem, which approximates the original problem, is generated and solved by using Newton’s method. Since it only requires first-order sensitivity to approximate the subproblem, it is very efficient

for structural optimization problems, which require expensive function evaluations. Moreover, the method is globally convergent. From any starting point, the iteration points converge towards the set of Karush-Kuhn-Tucker points.

4 Numerical examples

MMA has been coded in Matlab and tested on different problems. It was quite stable and computationally efficient. The convergence of the method is illustrated by the fig.7.

Fig.7: Convergence of the function "Mass"

Finally, it was necessary to compare the mass of a lattice structure with those of the other composite or metal structures. The result is showed in fig.8.

Fig.8: Dependence of the normalized mass on the axial force: (1) lattice structure, (2) stiffened metal shell, (3) sandwich metal shell

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